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Use of desert sand to synthesize MgSiO_3 -SiC composite ceramics

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Introduction

- ◆ Dense protoenstatite ceramics are good candidates for refractory and electronic assemblies.
- ◆ Decrease in temperature induces a transformation of the protoenstatite to clinoenstatite that results in cracking of ceramic bodies.
- ◆ Glass phase or a secondary phase can stabilize the microstructure and strengthen the ceramics by introducing the low-purity SiO_2 compounds such as desert-sand and SiC particles.
- ◆ The natural desert-sand consisted of silica and a small amount of CaO, TiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 and MgO, which are a tremendous SiO_2 resource, industrial applications of which are great significant to economize minerals and improve the desert ecological environment.

Desert distribution in China and in the world

Desert dunes

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Phase diagram of SiO_2 - MgO (- Al_2O_3) system

Physicochemical characters of the sands

Table 1 Main composition of the drift-sands

Compositions	Percentage, wt%
SiO ₂	78.91
Al ₂ O ₃	9.50
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.26
CaO	2.33
K ₂ O	2.08
Na ₂ O	2.00
MgO	0.86
TiO ₂	0.31

Fig. 1 Drift-sand with an average size of about 150 µm

Fig.2 Phase transformation of the sands

Experimental procedures

The desert-sand (76.7 wt% SiO₂, Hobq desert in Inner-Mongolia of China), industrial MgO and SiC were used as raw materials.

Desert-sand and MgO powders were batched with a stoichiometric composition of MgSiO₃; SiC powders were added to form composite powders and wet-milled.

The dried composite powders were pressed into disks and bending bars under a unidirectional pressure of 50 MPa. All of the samples were sintered at different temperatures for 2 h in air atmosphere.

Sintering, microstructure and properties of the composite ceramics

Fig. 3 Variation of the porosity with the sintering temperature and SiC addition

Fig. 4 Surface morphology of samples containing 30 wt% SiC at (a) 1250 °C, (b) 1300 °C, (c) 1350 °C; (d) 1400 °C

Fig.5 Element distribution in ceramic

Fig. 6 XRD patterns of samples sintered at (a) 1300°C, (b) 1350°C, (● protoenstatite, ◆ SiC, ○ forsterite, + SiO₂)

Fig. 7 Thermal expansion coefficient of the composite ceramics

Fig.8 Mechanical properties of composite ceramics. (a) Bending strength; (b) Vickers-hardness

Conclusions

Use of the drift sands yielded a glass phase, which ensures the crack-free ceramics and improved the protoenstatite transformation and densification.

Addition of SiC reduced the densification of green bodies; which was lightened by increasing the sintering temperature.

The ceramic containing 30 wt% of SiC and sintering at 1350°C had the highest strength.